

Report on Link to Global Wind Atlas and National Wind Atlases Deliverable D4.7

Edited by: Jake Badger
Delivery date: First draft, 28 Feb 2018
Dissemination level: Public

Author Information

Name	Organisation	E-mail
Jake Badger	DTU Wind Energy, DK	jaba@dtu.dk
Anna Maria	DTU Wind Energy, DK	anse@dtu.dk
Stefan Söderberg	Weathertech, SE	stefan@weathertech.se
Paula Alexandra Costa	LNEG, PT	paula.alexandracosta@lneg.pt
Teresa Simoes	LNET, PT	teresa.simoes@lneg.pt
Ana Estanqueiro	LNEG, PT	ana.estanqueiro@lneg.pt
Julia Gottschall	Fraunhofer IWES, DE	julia.gottschall@iwes.fraunhofer.de
Martin Dörenkämper	Fraunhofer IWES, DE	martin.dorenkaemper@iwes.fraunhofer.de
Doron Callies	Fraunhofer IEE, DE	doron.callies@iee.fraunhofer.de
Jorge Navarro Montesinos	CIEMAT, ES	jorge.navarro@ciemat.es
Fidel	UCM, ES	fidelgr@fis.ucm.es
Elena Garcia Bustamante	UCM, ES	elgarcia@ucm.es
Ides Bauwens	Nazka Mapps, BE	ides@nazka.be

Table of Contents

Table of Contents	ii
Executive Summary	iii
1. Introduction	1
2. Global Wind Atlas v1	2
3. Global Wind Atlas v2	4
4. Portuguese onshore wind atlas	5
5. Portuguese onshore wind energy atlas (Portugal, Madeira and Azores Islands) for SWT 7	
6. NORSEWInD: Northern sea offshore wind atlas	10
7. WASA (Wind and Stability Atlas) for the Southern North Sea	13
8. Wind atlases for Germany	15
Wind atlas for Rhineland-Palatinate	16
Wind resource map for Hesse	17
Anemos wind atlas for Germany	18
9. IDEA Wind Atlas for Spain	20
10. Swedish wind atlas	22
11. Finnish wind atlas	24
12. Norwegian wind atlas	26
13. European Wind Atlas	29
14. Summary	31
Acknowledgements	1

Executive Summary

This document provides information for numerous wind atlas, relevant to the New European Wind Atlas. It uses the taxonomy and metadata card format, developed for the wind energy sector and wind resource assessment, in particular, by the European collaborators within the IPRWind project. By using this taxonomy various aspects the wind atlases can be as compared and features in common can be examined.

1. Introduction

Over the last 30 years numerous wind atlas have been calculated with coverage over the European region either wholly or in part. The diversity of the methods used to create the wind atlases and the manner in which the data can be used and how it is disseminated are described in this report. The taxonomy developed with the EERA IRPWind project is employed for the first time in order to organize the attributes of the wind atlases, in the form of the wind atlas “metadata card”.

As well as collecting metadata for relevant wind atlas, this report also allows for exploration of potential links between the New European Wind Atlas to these wind atlases where appropriate.

Potential linkages include: databases for inputs, methodology for calculation, methodology for validation, methodology for dissemination, webpage development.

2. Global Wind Atlas v1

Description: A modelling based wind atlas using input data from MERRA reanalysis downscaled directly to microscale using a WAsP based calculation system, with roughness length derived from Globcover land uses classes and surface elevation from ViewFinder terrain dataset. Funding from Danish Energy Agency EUDP 11-II,64011-0347.

Link: science.globalwindatlas.info

Metadata Card:

1. Title	GWA1.0
2. Creator	DTU Wind Energy
3. Topic*	Wind Atlases
4. Description	A modelling based wind atlas using input data from MERRA reanalysis downscaled directly to microscale using a WAsP based calculation system, with roughness length derived from Globcover land uses classes and surface elevation from ViewFinder terrain dataset. Funding from Danish Energy Agency EUDP 11-II, 64011-0347.
5. Publisher	Published on own website
6. Contributor	DTU Wind Energy
7. Date	1993-01-01 to 2014-12-31
8. Type*	modelled
9. Format	geotiff, json, txt, WAsP libfile
10. Identifier	DOI of the Atlas or publication references
11. Source	MERRA, Globcover, Viewfinder
12. Language	en-GB
13. Relations	NONE
14. Coverage	Global
15. Rights (accessRights)	Open
16. Variables*	Wind speed, wind direction, power density, terrain orography, roughness, wind speed distribution
17. External conditions*	All
18. Activity*	Modelling
19. Instrument*	NONE
20. Model*	Reanalysis, Mesoscale, WAsP
21. Material*	NONE

Potential linkages to New European Wind Atlas:

Some of the online analysis tools developed for the Global Wind Atlas v1 can be extended for use in NEWA, including diurnal cycle and annual cycle plotting. The roughness and elevation input files for the microscale modelling can be used as baseline reference for more advanced NEWA microscale modelling inputs.

3. Global Wind Atlas v2

Description: An update on the Global Wind Atlas v1. A modelling based wind atlas using input data from ERA-Interim reanalysis downscaled via mesoscale modelling using WRF and then to microscale using a WAsP based calculation system, with roughness length derived from Globcover land uses classes and surface elevation from ViewFinder terrain dataset. Funding from World Bank.

Link: www.globalwindatlas.info

Metadata Card:

1. Title	GWA2.0
2. Creator	DTU Wiind Energy, Vortex, Nazka Mapps
3. Topic*	Wind Atlases
4. Description	An update on the Global Wind Atlas v1. A modelling based wind atlas using input data from ERA-Interim reanalysis downscaled via mesoscale modelling using WRF and then to microscale using a WAsP based calculation system, with roughness length derived from Globcover land uses classes and surface elevation. from ViewFinder terrain dataset. Funded from World Bank.
5. Publisher	Published on own website
6. Contributor	DTU Wind Energy
7. Date	1987-01-01 to 2016-12-31
8. Type*	modelled
9. Format	geotiff, json, txt, WAsP libfile
10. Identifier	DOI of the Atlas or publication references
11. Source	ERA-Interim, Globcover, Viewfinder
12. Language	en-GB
13. Relations	New version of GWA1.0
14. Coverage	Global
15. Rights (accessRights)	Open
16. Variables*	Wind speed, wind direction, power density, terrain orography, roughness, wind speed distribution
17. External conditions*	All
18. Activity*	Modelling
19. Instrument*	NONE
20. Model*	Reanalysis, Mesoscale, WAsP
21. Material*	NONE

Potential linkages to New European Wind Atlas:

Nazka Mapps has developed the website for GWA2.0 this may inspire some further developments that be implemented in the NEWA website.

4. Portuguese onshore wind atlas

Description: The Portuguese onshore wind atlas was obtained using numerical modeling with the mesoscale atmospheric model MM5, version 3.7, with 4 one way-nested domains up to 3x3km spatial resolution using input data from NCAR's Reanalysis database Project. The terrain and land uses classes and roughness length information were derived from USGS databases at 1x1km.

Link: <http://geoportal.ineg.pt/geoportal/mapas/index.html?mapa=AtlasEolico>

Metadata Card:

1. Title	The Portuguese onshore Wind Atlas
2. Creator	LNEG
3. Topic*	Wind Atlases
4. Description	The Portuguese onshore wind atlas was modelling with the mesoscale atmospheric model MM5, version 3.7, with 4 one way-nested domains up to 3x3km spatial resolution using input data from NCAR's Reanalysis database Project. The terrain and land uses classes and roughness length information was derived from USGS databases at 1x1km. the atlas covers the whole mainland territory.
5. Publisher	LNEG. Own website.
6. Contributor	LNEGs
7. Date	2004-01-01 to up to date
8. Type*	Modelled
9. Format	Geotiff, ASC, GRD, TXT, WAsP libfile
10. Identifier	Costa P., P. Miranda, A. Estanqueiro (2006) "The Development and Validation of the Portuguese Wind Atlas". In the Proceedings of the European Wind Energy Conference, 2006, Athens. ISBN: 972-676-196-4
11. Source	NCAR Reanalysis Project
12. Language	PT but it can be translated to UK-US
13. Relations	NONE
14. Coverage	Continental (Mainland) Portugal
15. Rights (accessRights)	Open
16. Variables*	Wind speed, wind speed components, wind direction, power density, weibull parameters, Number of hours at full capacity
17. External conditions*	onshore, coastal onshore, complex, flat, forest, rural, semi-urban
18. Activity*	Modelling
19. Instrument*	4 anemometric stations equipped at two heighs with wind speed and vane sensors for validation / calibration of the atlas
20. Model*	Reanalysis, Mesoscale, MM5 Version 3.7
21. Material*	NONE

Potential linkages to New European Wind Atlas:

The Portuguese onshore wind atlas provides useful information about wind speed and other meteorological variables including Temperature, Humidity, Wind Power production expressed in terms of number of hours at full capacity (wind power curve simulation of any wind turbine model), turbulence intensity among others, in particular for the Perdigão Region – which is the Portuguese Validation point for Complex Terrain in the NEWA project. The data is processed in different formats such as the GeoTiff, GRD, ASC, WAsP map files, WAsP Libfiles, WAsP resource grid files.

5. Portuguese onshore wind energy atlas (Portugal, Madeira and Azores Islands) for SWT

Description: The Portuguese onshore wind energy atlas for micro-generation purposes was modeled with the mesoscale atmospheric model MM5, version 3.7, with 4 one way-nested domains up to 1x1km spatial resolution using input data from NCAR's Reanalysis database Project. The terrain and land uses classes and roughness length information was derived from USGS databases at 1x1km for Portugal, Madeira and Azores Islands. The maps produced are expressed in number of hours at full capacity. The wind energy atlas follows the establishment in a Decree-Law DL80/2006 by the Portuguese Government.

Link: <http://geoportal.ineg.pt/geoportal/mapas/index.html?mapa=neps>

Metadata Card:

1. Title	The Portuguese (Portugal, Madeira and Azores) onshore wind energy atlas for micro-generation purposes respecting the decree-law DL80/2006 published by the Portuguese Government
2. Creator	LNEG
3. Topic*	Wind Atlases
4. Description	The Portuguese onshore wind energy atlas for micro-generation purposes was modeled with the mesoscale atmospheric model MM5, version 3.7, with 4 one way-nested domains up to 1x1km spatial resolution using input data from NCAR's Reanalysis database Project. The terrain and land uses classes and roughness length information was derived from USGS databases at 1x1km for Portugal, Madeira and Azores Islands. The maps produced are expressed in number of hours at full capacity. The wind energy atlas follows the establish in a Decree-Law DL80/2006 by the Portuguese Government.
5. Publisher	Published on own website
6. Contributor	LNEG
7. Date	2006-05-05 to up to date
8. Type*	Modelled
9. Format	GeoTiff, ASC, GRD, TXT and Inquiring values
10. Identifier	Costa P., P. Miranda, A. Estanqueiro (2006) "The Development and Validation of the Portuguese Wind Atlas". In the Proceedings of the European Wind Energy Conference, 2006, Athens.
11. Source	NCAR Reanalysis Project
12. Language	PT only
13. Relations	NONE
14. Coverage	Continental Portugal, Madeira and Azores Islands
15. Rights (accessRights)	Open
16. Variables*	Wind speed, wind speed components, number of hours at full capacity at 10m and 20m height above terrain surface
17. External conditions*	onshore, coastal onshore, complex, flat, forest, rural, urban and semi-urban
18. Activity*	Modelling
19. Instrument*	4 anemometric stations equipped at two heights with wind speed and vane sensors for validation / calibration of the wind speed
20. Model*	Reanalysis, Mesoscale, MM5 Version 3.7
21. Material*	NONE

Potential linkages to New European Wind Atlas:

The Portuguese onshore wind energy atlas provide useful information about wind speed and wind power production expressed in terms of number of hours at full capacity (wind power curve simulation of any urban-wind turbine model) at heights of 10m and 20m above surface terrain. The wind information at high resolution can be used particularly for the Perdigoão Region – which is the Portuguese Validation point for Complex Terrain

for the NEWA project. The data is processed in different formats such as the GeoTiff, GRD, ASC, or WASP resource grid files.

6. NORSEWInD: Northern sea offshore wind atlas

Description: The Northern Sea offshore wind atlas comprises the offshore wind atlas for the Northern, Irish, Baltic and West Portuguese Sea areas for the FP7 NORSEWInD project (<http://www.norsewind.eu>). The wind atlas was based on modelling with the mesoscale atmospheric model WRF, version 3.2, with 3 one-way nested domains up to 2x2km spatial resolution for all offshore areas. The main input data was provided from the Final Global Data Assimilation system (FNL) database and the terrain and landuses classes and roughness length information was derived from the USGS databases at 1x1km.

Link: <http://geoportal.ineg.pt/geoportal/mapas/index.html?mapa=Norsewind>

Metadata Card:

1. Title	The Northern Sea offshore wind atlas - FP7 NORSEWInD Project
2. Creator	FP7-NORSEWInD Project
3. Topic*	Wind Atlases
4. Description	The Northern Sea offshore wind atlas comprises the offshore wind atlas for the Northern, Irish, Baltic and West Portuguese Coast provided for the FP7 NORSEWInD project (http://www.norsewind.eu). The wind atlas was modelling with the mesoscale atmospheric model WRF, version 3.2, with 3 one-way nested domains up to 2x2km spatial resolution for all sea space areas. The main input data was provided from the Final Global Data Assimilation system (FNL) database and the terrain and land uses classes and roughness length information was derived from the USGS databases at 1x1km.
5. Publisher	Published on LNEG's on own website and the FP7-NORSEWInD project website
6. Contributor	FP7-NORSEWInD partners
7. Date	2008-09-01 to 2012-09-30
8. Type*	Modelled
9. Format	GeoTiff, ASC, GRD, TXT, WAsP Libfile
10. Identifier	<p>Marujo R., P. Costa, M. Fernandes, T. Simões, A. Estanqueiro (2013) "Validation of an offshore wind atlas using the satellite data available at the coastal regions of Portugal". Journal of Wind Engineering, Vol 37, Nr. 4, 2013, pp321-332.</p> <p>Fernandes M., P. Costa, A. Estanqueiro (2011) "Improving offshore wind resource assessment using a data assimilation technique. Proceedings of the European Wind Energy Association, Brussels, 2011.</p> <p>Berge, E.; Byrkjedal, O.; Ydersbond, Y.; Kindler, D. 'Modelling of offshore wind resources. Comparison of a meso-scale model and measurements from FINO-1 and North Sea oil rigs'. Scientific Proceedings EWEC'09 Marseille, March 2009.</p> <p>Costa P., T. Simões, A. Estanqueiro. "Assessment of the Sustainable Offshore Wind Potential in Portugal" European Wind Energy Conference (EWEC), Athens, 2006.</p>
11. Source	Final Global Data Assimilation Reanalysis system (FNL)
12. Language	en-US
13. Relations	None
14. Coverage	Northern, Baltic, Irish, Western Portuguese sea areas
15. Rights (accessRights)	Open
16. Variables*	Wind speed, wind speed components, wind direction, power density, wind uncertainties
17. External conditions*	Offshore
18. Activity*	Modelling
19. Instrument*	Several anemometric masts and ZephIR Lidar systems and Satellite data for validation / calibration of the atlas
20. Model*	Reanalysis, Mesoscale, WRF Version 3.2
21. Material*	None

Potential linkages to New European Wind Atlas:

The Northern Sea offshore wind atlas can provide useful information about wind speed and other different variables including wind uncertainties over the ocean particularly for the northern sea area near Denmark where is designated a local point for offshore validation for the NEWA project. All data is processed in different compatible formats such as the GeoTiff, GRD, ASC, WASP map files, WASP Libfiles, WASP resource grid files.

7. WASA (Wind and Stability Atlas) for the Southern North Sea

Description: The Wind And Stability Atlas (WASA) provides information on the climatology of wind and stability conditions in the southern North Sea. It was primarily generated with the objective to provide a source of input data for the wake modelling tools within the ClusterDesign tool box that was developed in the EU-FP7-project ClusterDesign. The atlas provides time series as well as statistics in file size optimized NetCDF-files.

Link: A presentation with some details on the WASA can be found under https://www.cluster-design.eu/db/WAS571494a2a162a/02_FP7_Workshop_Flow_modelling_for_wind_farm_clusters_final_150416.pdf . There is no webpage exclusively dedicated to the presentation of the WASA.

Metadata Card:

1. Title	WASA - Wind And Stability Atlas for the North Sea
2. Creator	ForWind, Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg
3. Topic*	Wind Atlases
4. Description	The atlas was derived by the means of dynamical downscaling of CFSR reanalysis data for the period from 1993-2012 with the means of the meso-scale model WRF.
5. Publisher	ClusterDesign consortium, part of the ClusterDesign tool box
6. Contributor	ForWind, Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg
7. Date	2011-12-01 - 2016-05-31
8. Type*	Modeled
9. Format	NetCDF
10. Identifier	
11. Source	NONE
12. Language	en-US
13. Relations	NONE
14. Coverage	coordinates of the corner points of the WASA domain are 51.880°N 3.0380°E in the southwest, 53.7708°N 9.3970°E in the southeast, 53.5870°N 1.4463°E in the northeast and 55.5611°N 8.0094°E in the northwest.
15. Rights (accessRights)	Access to the WASA can be obtained by contacting gerald.steinfeld@uni-oldenburg.de, access conditions have to be negotiated with the administration of Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg
16. Variables*	see the related sheet
17. External conditions*	
18. Activity*	
19. Instrument*	
20. Model*	see the related sheet
21. Material*	

Potential linkages to New European Wind Atlas:

For the NEWA wind atlas some information on how the file sizes could be minimized for the WASA wind atlas might be of interested.

Note: In order to minimize the size of the final WASA all variables have been saved as integer values and therefore been multiplied with a scaling factor prior to the output into the NetCDF file. The scaling factors are provided as attributes to the variables in the NetCDF file. Hence, the rescaling is already done automatically by certain NetCDF postprocessors, as e.g. the visualization tool ncview.

To further minimize the file sizes the NetCDF files have been compressed by using the command nccopy with the highest possible deflation level of 9. By this, the size of a time series file for a single point containing twenty years of data can finally be reduced to about 40 MB.

8. Wind atlases for Germany

There is nothing like one “Wind atlas for Germany”. Discussions on the initiation of a respective project have been existing for the last couple of years but not related to larger activities.

However, there have been several activities on state level and, at the same time, there are several commercial providers offering wind maps and time series for specific regions or the complete federal territory on request.

Wind atlases on state level include the:

- Wind atlas for Saxony
- Wind resource study (wind atlas) for North Rhine-Westphalia
- Wind atlas for Bavaria
- Wind atlas for Baden-Württemberg
- Wind atlas for Rhineland-Palatinate
- Wind resource map for Hesse
- Wind resource study for Saarland

It was found to be rather difficult to collect all the details that are requested for the metadata cards for all of these products – in particular, since they have been provided by different institutions and companies. Therefore, we do not introduce all of them but only further detail the atlases/maps for Saxony, Rhineland-Palatinate and Hesse – see the metadata cards and short introductions below.

An example of a wind atlas that is provided on a fully commercial level is the Anemos Wind atlas for Germany, which is also specified in some detail further below.

Wind atlas for Saxony¹

Description: [source (press release) <http://w3.windmesse.de/windenergie/pm/26552-portal-arge-saxwind-geo-net-windatlas-sachsen>]

As part of the ARGE SaxWind GEO-NET Umweltconsulting GmbH produced a wind atlas for the complete state of Saxony. The wind atlas is publicly accessible through the ‘Energieportal Sachsen’.

In addition to publicly accessible wind data a comprehensive planning tool is available to the expert user. The wind atlas serves the state ministry for the update of regional plans and shows in detail the wind resources of the state of Saxony with a resolution of 100 m in different heights above ground level.

¹ Description and metadata by J. Gottschall, Fraunhofer IWES

Description:

Link: <http://www.energieportal-sachsen.de/>

Metadata Card:

1. Title	Wind atlas for Saxony (Germany)
2. Creator	
3. Topic*	Wind Atlases
4. Description	application of mesoscale model FITNAH-3D, results verified with comprehensive reference database; portal provides wind resource map comprising energy density and mean wind speed at four height levels (70 m, 100 m, 130 m, 160 m) above ground
5. Publisher	state of Saxoy
6. Contributor	
7. Date	
8. Type*	modeled
9. Format	
10. Identifier	
11. Source	
12. Language	
13. Relations	
14. Coverage	state of Saxony
15. Rights (accessRights)	open access
16. Variables*	
17. External conditions*	
18. Activity*	
19. Instrument*	
20. Model*	
21. Material*	

Wind atlas for Rhineland-Palatinate²

Description:

The wind atlas for Rhineland-Palatinate is a wind map of 50mx50m. The microscale model used is O.F.Wind. The average wind speed was calculated for heights of 100m to 160 m. To ensure the quality the wind atlas was verified and refined with 773 wind turbines.

² Description and metadata provided by D. Callies, Fraunhofer IEE

Link(s):

https://mwkel.rlp.de/fileadmin/mwkel/rlp_windatlas_stand_24072013.pdf

<https://mueef.rlp.de/de/themen/energie-und-strahlenschutz/erneuerbare-energien/windenergie>

by TÜV Süd 5 line description

Metadata Card:

1. Title	Windatlas Rheinland-Pfanz
2. Creator	TÜV SÜD IS GmbH
3. Topic*	Wind Atlases
4. Description	The wind atlas for Rhineland-Palatinate is a wind map of 50mx50m. The microscale model used is O.F.Wind. The average wind speed was calculated for heights of 100m to 160 m. To ensure the quality the wind atlas was verified and refined with 773 wind turbines.
5. Publisher	Ministerium für Wirtschaft, Klimaschutz, Energie und Landesplanung Rheinland-Pfalz
6. Contributor	
7. Date	2013
8. Type*	
9. Format	shape, GeoTiff, ASCII Raster
10. Identifier	https://mwkel.rlp.de/fileadmin/mwkel/rlp_windatlas_stand_24072013.pdf
11. Source	
12. Language	
13. Relations	
14. Coverage	Rhineland-Palatinate
15. Rights (accessRights)	see web page
16. Variables*	see the related sheet
17. External conditions*	see the related sheet
18. Activity*	see the related sheet
19. Instrument*	see the related sheet
20. Model*	see the related sheet
21. Material*	see the related sheet

Wind resource map for Hesse³

Description:

The wind resource map of Hesse shows the average wind speed in 80m, 100m and 140m height and has a horizontal resolution of 100m x 100m. Additionally Weibull parameters and wind direction frequencies were derived. The input data used are mainly weather stations and the map was validated using wind farm production data.

³ Description and metadata provided by D. Callies, Fraunhofer IEE

Link(s):

https://www.energieland.hessen.de/pdf/Windpotenzialkarte_Hessen_-_Bericht.pdf

https://www.energieland.hessen.de/pdf/Windpotenzialkarte_Hessen_-_Uebersicht_140m.pdf

Metadata Card:

1. Title	Windressourcenkarte Hessen
2. Creator	TÜV SÜD IS GmbH
3. Topic*	Wind Atlases
4. Description	The wind resource map of Hesse shows the average wind speed in 80m, 100m and 140m height and has a horizontal resolution of 100m x 100m. Additionally Weibull parameters and wind direction frequencies were derived. The input data used are mainly weather stations and the data were validated using wind farm production data.
5. Publisher	Hessisches Ministerium für Umwelt, Energie, Landwirtschaft und Verbraucherschutz (HMUVELV)
6. Contributor	
7. Date	2011
8. Type*	Observations
9. Format	pdf
10. Identifier	https://www.energieland.hessen.de/pdf/Windpotenzialkarte_Hessen_-_Uebersicht_140m.pdf
11. Source	
12. Language	German
13. Relations	
14. Coverage	Hesse
15. Rights (accessRights)	
16. Variables*	see the related sheet
17. External conditions*	see the related sheet
18. Activity*	see the related sheet
19. Instrument*	see the related sheet
20. Model*	O.F.Wind
21. Material*	see the related sheet

Anemos wind atlas for Germany⁴

Description:

anemos wind atlas (D-3km.Me*(remodelling)) for Germany is a mesoscale modeled wind atlas using WRF in combination with MERRA 2. It is verified with wind measurements and remodeled afterwards to ensure a high quality.

⁴ Description and metadata provided by D. Callies, Fraunhofer IEE

Link: <http://www.anemos.de/files/windatlanten/Dokumentation-D-3km.M2.pdf>

Following the same concept, anemos also produced other wind atlases (regions France, Belgium, Poland, Switzerland and Europe)

Link: <http://www.anemos.de/en/windatlas.php>

Metadata Card:

1. Title	D-3km.Me*(remodelling)
2. Creator	anemos Gesellschaft für Umweltmeteorologie mbH
3. Topic*	Wind Atlases
4. Description	anemos wind atlas (D-3km.Me*(remodelling)) for Germany is a mesoscale modeled wind atlas using WRF and MERRA 2. It is verified with wind measurements and remodeled afterwards to ensure a high quality.
5. Publisher	anemos Gesellschaft für Umweltmeteorologie mbH
6. Contributor	
7. Date	1997-ongoing
8. Type*	modeled
9. Format	Time series
10. Identifier	http://www.anemos.de/files/windatlanten/Dokumentation-D-3km.M2.pdf
11. Source	
12. Language	
13. Relations	
14. Coverage	Germany
15. Rights (accessRights)	anemos Gesellschaft für Umweltmeteorologie mbH
16. Variables*	wind speed, wind direction, other
17. External conditions*	all
18. Activity*	modeled
19. Instrument*	masts
20. Model*	reanalysis, mesoscale, WRF
21. Material*	

9. IDEA Wind Atlas for Spain

Description: The Spanish wind atlas designed by IDEA has been developed by Meteosim Truewind and was obtained with the MASS (Mesoscale Atmospheric Simulation System) limited area numerical model coupled with WinMap (mass conservation model). The wind atlas has two horizontal resolutions at 2.5 km and 100 m, and uses its input data from NCAR's Reanalysis (15 years), SRTM and Corine Land Cover.

Link: <http://atlaseolico.idae.es/meteosim/>

Metadata Card:

1. Title	IDAE Wind Atlas of Spain
2. Creator	The Institute for Diversification and Saving of Energy (IDAE, http://www.idae.es/en) sponsored the atlas. It was developed by the company Meteosim Truewind
3. Topic*	Wind Atlases
4. Description	The Spanish wind atlas designed by IDAE has been developed by Meteosim Truewind. It was obtained using the regional numerical model MASS (Mesoscale Atmospheric Simulation System) coupled with WinMap (mass conservation model). The wind atlas has two horizontal resolutions at 2.5 km and 100 m, and uses input data from NCAR's Reanalysis (15 years), SRTM and Corine Land Cover.
5. Publisher	IDAE
6. Contributor	IDAE
7. Date	15 years (unspecified dates)
8. Type*	Mesoscale simulation
9. Format	Interactive maps with interactive pop-up windows, and pdf files with wind resources information
10. Identifier	Technical report in Spanish (http://www.idae.es/uploads/documentos/documentos_11227_e4_atlas_eolico_A_9b90ff10.pdf) DOI of the Atlas or publication references
11. Source	http://atlaseolico.idae.es/meteosim/
12. Language	en-GB and Spanish
13. Relations	Other Atlas developed by Meteosim Truewind
14. Coverage	Iberian Peninsula, Balearic and Canary Island
15. Rights (accessRights)	Open
16. Variables*	For wind resource it contains the wind roses at 80 m at the 2.5 km resolution, and the anual and seasonal wind speed at 100 m. Wind maps of anual mean wind speed (m/s) at 30, 60, 80 and 100m; wind power density (W/m^2) at the same levels; and seasonal wind speed (m/s) at 80 m. It also offers the annual mean air density (kg/m^3) at 80m; the annual mean atmospheric pressure (hPa) at 80 m; and the annual mean temperatura ($^{\circ}C$) at 80 m. Other information available: topography and surface roughness, administrative boundaries, protected areas, the EEAL Zoning - Marine Wind Farming, the 'Environmental Figures', as National Parks, etc. and cadastral references.
17. External conditions*	All
18. Activity*	Modelling
19. Instrument*	NONE
20. Model*	Reanalysis, Mesoscale, Microscale
21. Material*	NONE

Potential linkages to New European Wind Atlas:

The IDAE wind atlas could provide useful information about wind speed, wind direction and power density, although its use for the purposes of the NEWA project might not be feasible since the available format for downloading is just pdf.

10. Swedish wind atlas

Description: The higher-order closure MIUU-model has been used to map the wind climate using the MIUU-method, developed at Uppsala University. This method reduces the total number of simulations needed to 192 climatologically relevant daily cycles representing different wind and temperature (seasonal) conditions. The results are weighted together based on climatological data for the geostrophic wind in order to finally estimate the wind climate. To use this method geostrophic wind (strength and direction), sea and land temperatures, topography, roughness, and land use are needed. No observed boundary-layer winds are used other than for verification. Comparisons between model results and measurements show good agreement

Link: <http://www.energimyndigheten.se/fornybart/vindkraft/planering-och-tillstand/vindkraftsplanering1/nationell-vindkartering/>

Metadata Card:

1. Title	Nationell vindkartering
2. Creator	WeatherTech Scandinavia AB
3. Topic*	Wind Atlases
4. Description	The higher-order closure MIUU-model has been used to map the wind climate using the MIUU-method, developed at Uppsala University. This method reduces the total number of simulations needed to 192 climatologically relevant daily cycles representing different wind and temperature (seasonal) conditions. The results are weighted together based on climatological data for the geostrophic wind in order to finally estimate the wind climate. To use this method geostrophic wind (strength and direction), sea and land temperatures, topography, roughness, and land use are needed. No observed boundary-layer winds are used other than for verification. Comparisons between model results and measurements show good agreement.
5. Publisher	Energimyndigheten
6. Contributor	WeatherTech
7. Date	Climatology based on 30 years reanalysis data, 1981-2010.
8. Type*	Modelled
9. Format	txt, png, shape files
10. Identifier	Bergström, H. and Söderberg, S., 2012. Beräkning av vindklimatet i Sverige med 0,25 km ² upplösning med hjälp av miuu-modellen.
11. Source	Corine, NCAR, Metria
12. Language	Swedish
13. Relations	Update of national wind resource map. Model grid resolution increased from 1 km ² to 0.25km ² . Source for landuse changed from USGS to Corine.
14. Coverage	Sweden
15. Rights (accessRights)	Open
16. Variables*	Wind speed, wind direction, roughness, terrain
17. External conditions*	Onshore and coastal
18. Activity*	Modelling
19. Instrument*	Wind measurements from 122 tall met masts have been used for validation of the atlas. Measurement heights vary between 20m and 145m; most measurements are in the interval 40m to 100m.
20. Model*	NCAR/NCEP Reanalysis, MIUU model (mesoscale), MIUU method (climatology)
21. Material*	NONE

Potential linkages to New European Wind Atlas:

A verified wind atlas using a different model and method to estimate the wind resources which can be used for comparisons.

11. Finnish wind atlas

Description: The Wind Atlas is produced by the European numerical weather forecasting model AROME (2.5 km grid resolution) and by the Danish Wind Application and Analysis Program WASP (downscaling to 250 m grid at selected areas). The WASP data is produced as monthly means without distribution into wind direction sectors for heights from 50 m to 150 m or 200 m. The WASP lib-files are given for each 2.5 km grid. The atlas also gives maps with estimates of active and passive icing, and production loss to due to icing.

Link: <http://www.tuuliatlas.fi/en/>

Metadata Card:

1. Title	Finnish Wind Atlas
2. Creator	Finnish Meteorological Institute
3. Topic*	Wind Atlases
4. Description	The Wind Atlas is produced by the European numerical weather forecasting model AROME (2.5 km grid resolution) and by the Danish Wind Application and Analysis Program WAsP (downscaling to 250 m grid at selected areas). The WAsP data is produced as monthly means without distribution into wind direction sectors for heights from 50 m to 150 m or 200 m. The WAsP lib-files are given for each 2.5 km grid. The atlas also gives maps with estimates of active and passive icing, and production loss to due to icing.
5. Publisher	Finnish Meteorological Institute
6. Contributor	Finnish Meteorological Institute and DTU Wind Energy
7. Date	1987-1-1 to 2007-12-31
8. Type*	Modelled
9. Format	WAsP lib-files and JPEG files of maps
10. Identifier	Tammelin, B, Vihma, T, Atlaskin, E, Badger, J, Fortelius, C, Gregow, H, Horttanainen, M, Hyvönen, R, Kilpinen, J, Latikka, J, Ljungberg, K, Mortensen, NG, Niemelä, S, Ruosteenoja, K, Salonen, K, Suomi, I & Venäläinen, A 2013, 'Production of the Finnish Wind Atlas' Wind Energy, vol 16, pp. 19-35. DOI: 10.1002/we.517
11. Source	ERA-Intrim, AROME roughness and elevation data
12. Language	fi, en-GB
13. Relations	NONE
14. Coverage	Finland
15. Rights (accessRights)	available from http://www.tuuliatlas.fi/en/
16. Variables*	wind speed, wind direction, wind speed distributions, active icing, passive icing, production losses due to icing
17. External conditions*	onshore and offshoe
18. Activity*	modelling
19. Instrument*	NONE
20. Model*	ERA-Intrim, HIRLAM, AROME, WAsP
21. Material*	NONE

Potential linkages to New European Wind Atlas:

The Finnish Wind Atlas was one of the first atlases to deliver high resolution predicted wind climates using a web interface. Therefore aspects of the web interface has been of interest for the Global Wind Atlas and New European Wind Atlas, with the use of open source map engine and standard web service protocols.

12. Norwegian wind atlas

Description: The Norwegian Wind Map was developed in 2009 by Kjeller Vindteknikk on commission by the Norwegian Water Resource and Energy Directorate (NVE). The wind map was generated by the use of the Weather Research and Forecast model (WRF) which was run with a grid resolution of 1 km x 1 km covering all of the country. The simulations were carried out for the full year of 2005 and long term corrected toward the period 2000-2008 using a coarser WRF setup (5 km grid resolution). The Norwegian wind map is presented at three heights; 50 m, 80 m and 120 m above the surface. In addition to the wind map a map showing the energy production of a generic wind turbine was created and an icing map showing the number of meteorological icing hours per year. The maps and reports from this project are available from the web pages of NVE in pdf format. The maps can also be displayed through NVE's online mapping tools.

Links:

<https://www.nve.no/energiforsyning-og-konsesjon/vindkraft/vindressurser/>
<https://gis3.nve.no/link/?link=vindressurser>

Metadata Card:

1. Title	Vindkart for Norge
2. Creator	Kjeller Vindteknikk
3. Topic*	Wind Atlases
4. Description	The Norwegian Wind Map was developed in 2009 by Kjeller Vindteknikk on commission by the Norwegian Water Resource and Energy Directorate (NVE). The wind map was generated by the use of the Weather Research and Forecast model (WRF) which was run with a grid resolution of 1 km x 1 km covering all of the country. The simulations were carried out for the full year of 2005 and long term corrected toward the period 2000-2008 using a coarser WRF setup (5 km grid resolution). The Norwegian wind map is presented at three heights; 50 m, 80 m and 120 m above the surface. In addition to the wind map a map showing the energy production of a generic wind turbine was created and an icing map showing the number of meteorological icing hours per year. The maps and reports from this project are available from the web pages of NVE in pdf format. The maps can also be displayed through NVE's online mapping tools.
5. Publisher	Norges vassdrags- og energidirektorat
6. Contributor	Kjeller Vindteknikk
7. Date	2000-01-01 to 2008-12-31
8. Type*	Modelled
9. Format	pdf maps, available as ArcGIS raster upon request
10. Identifier	Byrkedal Ø. And Åkervik E. (2009). Vindkart for Norge, NVE oppdragsrapport A9/2009.
11. Source	NCEP Final Global Data Assimilation System (FNL), snow cover data from senorge.se, roughness and vegetation are based on N50 data from the national mapping authorities (Statens Kartverk)
12. Language	Norwegian
13. Relations	NONE
14. Coverage	Norway
15. Rights (accessRights)	According to Norwegian Licence for Open Government Data (NLOD) available from https://www.nve.no/energiforsyning-og-konsesjon/vindkraft/vindressurser https://gis3.nve.no/link/?link=vindressurser
16. Variables*	Average annual wind speed (m/s), wind energy production (full load hours), icing (number of active icing hours per year), Terrain complexity (RIX)
17. External conditions*	onshore and offshore
18. Activity*	modelling
19. Instrument*	NONE
20. Model*	WRF v 3.0.1, NCEP Final Global Data Assimilation System (FNL)
21. Material*	NONE

Potential linkages to New European Wind Atlas:

A validation of the wind map was carried out by comparing with 22 wind measurement masts (50 m to 80 m tall) that was in operation during 2005. For the concurrent time

periods this showed an average bias in the model calculations of 1.5%, mean absolute error of 5.9% and a standard deviation of 7.0%.

13. European Wind Atlas

Description: The European Wind Atlas was the first comprehensive wind atlas publication covering a number of European countries. It used the newly developed modelling elements within WASP to calculate generalized wind climates (WASP lib-file) from wind measurement data at large number of European measurement sites. The generalized wind climates can then be applied a nearby new sites.

Link: http://www.wasp.dk/dataandtools#wind-atlas_european-wind-atlas_download

Metadata Card:

1. Title	European Wind Atlas
2. Creator	Risø National Laboratory
3. Topic*	Wind Atlases
4. Description	This is a short Description of the process to derive the Atlas or whether there are other Atlases and the difference. Or references for publications.
5. Publisher	Risø National Laboratory, Roskilde, Denmark
6. Contributor	Ib Troen and Erik Lundtang Petersen, Risø National Laboratory
7. Date	approximately 1970/1/1 to 1979/12/31
8. Type*	Observations and modeled (WASP method)
9. Format	Printed book and WASP lib- and tab- files
10. Identifier	Troen, I. and E.L. Petersen (1989). European Wind Atlas. Risø National Laboratory, Roskilde. 656 pp. ISBN 87-550-1482-8.
11. Source	a related resource/dataset from which the described dataset is derived (in our case it will be NONE)
12. Language	en-GB, it, es, de, fr
13. Relations	NONE
14. Coverage	Belgium, Denmark, France, Germany (FRG), Greece, Ireland, Italy, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Portugal, Spain, United Kingdom
15. Rights (accessRights)	Free to download from orbit.dtu.dk/files/112135732/European_Wind_Atlas.pdf Hard copy (135 EURO) ordered from https://www.wasp.dk/DataandTools/EWA-orderform
16. Variables*	Wind speed, wind direction, power density, wind speed distribution
17. External conditions*	onshore
18. Activity*	measurement and modelling
19. Instrument*	cup anemometer
20. Model*	WASP
21. Material*	NONE

Potential linkages to New European Wind Atlas:

The European Wind Atlas is the predecessor to the New European Wind Atlas, so it sets a historic standard for usability of the data and method and documentation of the method itself. The usability of the data and method is made possible because of the access to the Generalized Wind Climate data files (lib-files) and the WAsP software. 30 years later WAsP, now at version 12, is used by 1200 active users daily.

14. Summary

This document describes provides information for numerous wind atlas, relevant to the New European Wind Atlas. It uses the taxonomy and metadata card format, developed for the wind energy sector and wind resource assessment in particular, developed by the European collaborators within the IPRWind project. By using this taxonomy various aspects the wind atlases can be as compared and features in common can be examined.

Acknowledgements

The NEWA project counts with the support from an ERA-Net Plus consortium composed by the European Commission and 9 funding agencies from 8 member states:

- Public Service of Wallonia, Department of Energy and Sustainable Building (Belgium)
- Department of Economy, Science and Innovation Flemish Government (Belgium)
- Danish Energy Authority (Denmark)
- Federal Ministry for the Economic Affairs and Energy, on the basis of the decision by the German Bundestag (Germany)
- Latvijas Zinatnu Akademija (Latvia)
- Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (Portugal)

- Ministerio de Economía y Competitividad (Spain)
- The Swedish Energy Agency (Sweden)

- The Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey (Turkey)